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Vtcn functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Vtcn as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.